

Original Article

Digital Dependency in Teens: Exploring the Impact of Blue Light and Parenting

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Abstract

The main aim of holding that study is to check that how mobile phone use affects addiction levels in teenagers and how parents' phone habits influence these behaviors. A cross-sectional study was conducted by using purposive sampling to survey 400 parents and their children with a standardized questionnaire containing 36 questions. The reliability of the questionnaire was checked by using Cronbach's Alpha, which showed a value of 0.698, indicating moderate consistency. Factor analysis revealed four key factors that explained 66.2% of the variance in mobile phone addiction behaviors. By using Confirmatory factor analysis, these factors confirmed. Multinomial logistic regression showed that parental mobile phone addiction has a significant effect on teenage addiction. The results emphasize the complex relationship between parental behavior and teenage mobile phone usage, offering insights for strategies to reduce mobile phone addiction in teenagers.

Keywords: Mobile Addiction, Blue Light, Confirmatory Factor Analysis, Multinomial Logistic Regression

Introduction

Teenagers' addiction to mobile phones has become a major concern in today's society. Excessive use of these devices can significantly impact their mental health. Mobile addiction, also known as smartphone addiction, is a type of behavioral addiction where people use their mobile devices too much and in a compulsive way. This can seriously affect their daily lives, including their social interactions, school performance, and personal well-being. Parents play a pivotal role in shaping their children's relationship with technology, and their own habits can greatly influence their children's behavior (Sharma, 2019). When parents are overly attached to their phones, it sets a norm that encourages similar behavior in their children. This can lead to a cycle of addiction, where teenagers spend excessive hours on their phones, neglecting other activities and relationships, and experiencing withdrawal symptoms when deprived of their devices. Research shows that 39.6% of teenagers in South Korea show signs of smartphone addiction, often reflecting the habits of their parents (Kim, 2021). The blue light from screens affects melatonin production, which is important for sleep. When sleep quality suffers, people often turn to their smartphones for socializing and entertainment, leading to a cycle of addiction. Research indicates that 67% of teens say they lose sleep because of phone use, which can worsen anxiety and stress (Emanuel et al., 2015).

In the U.S., 60% of college students think they are addicted to their smartphones, while 47% of parents feel their child is also addicted to their phone. The constant use of mobile phones can also contribute to psychological issues such as anxiety, depression, and sleep disturbances, which can have long-term effects on their mental health and overall well-being (De-Sola Gutiérrez et al., 2016). The anxiety of missing out (FOMO) prompts numerous individuals to check their devices regularly, which can lead to addictive behaviors (Choliz, 2012).

Statistics show that 83.9% of teenagers use smartphones, and about 37% of them show signs of addiction. Research suggests that teenagers use smartphones extensively (Bhanderi, Pandya & Sharma, 2021). Teens use their phones for seven hours a day on average, mostly for social media use. These platforms aim to increase user engagement by releasing dopamine into the brain through various techniques (Bahia, 2017). The frequent use of

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technology is associated with several adverse effects such as reduced sleep quality, problems with academic performance, and higher chances of accidents while driving (Kiran, Sanjana & Reddy, 2019).

Teens who are influenced by this may develop similar behaviors and start using their devices excessively, imitating their parents. Parental practices have a big impact on how their kids behave when using technology. When parents are absorbed in their gadgets, they might be less inclined to uphold regulations on their children's screen time. Consequently, this situation can lead to a normalization of excessive smartphone usage, which further solidifies addictive habits in teenagers (Ting & Chen, 2020). Elevated levels of parental conflict or insufficient parental oversight may result in heightened mobile phone usage, as adolescents often turn to their devices for validation or as a means of escape (Liu, Yang & Nie, 2023). It is found that 45% of teens use the internet "almost all the time," and 95% have smartphones, kids tend to imitate their parents' actions (Hurley, 2019).

Teenagers are increasingly struggling with mobile addiction, and blue light from screens is a big part of the problem. This blue light, found in smartphones, tablets, and computers, can interfere with sleep and lead to excessive phone use (Fardouly et al., 2015). Excessive use of electronic devices and exposure to blue light are major factors contributing to mobile addiction in teenagers. Smartphones have a strong appeal for teenagers, often keeping them engrossed for long periods, especially when they are already lacking sleep.

The vibrant screens and interactive features of mobile devices can result in prolonged use, worsened by the impact of blue light. Blue light exposure at night stops the body from making melatonin, a hormone that helps regulate sleep. Research indicates that even a small amount of blue light before bedtime can make it difficult to fall asleep and reduce sleep quality.

A study showed that teenagers who used devices with blue light slept less and had worse sleep, leading them to feel more tired during the day and rely more on screens for entertainment. Teenagers frequently engage in late-night scrolling through social media or gaming, further deepening their dependence on these devices (Leung, 2017). Artificial blue light disrupts melatonin production, causing hormonal imbalances and worse mental health outcomes (Silvani, Werder & Perret, 2022).

Sleep of teenagers becomes irregular, shortened, and delayed due to excessive use of cellphone or any other digital media, exposure to blue light from LEDs at night, and early school starting times on weekdays. This results in that case are desynchronization, loss of sleep, and health risks such as fatigue, daytime sleepiness, behavioral problems, and poor academic achievement (Rafique et al., 2020). Mobile phone addiction had a noteworthy direct impact on the quality of sleep as well as an indirect influence that was mediated by affect balance (Rathakrishnan et al., 2021). This implies that nomophobia is associated with elevated anxiety levels, increased smartphone addiction, and a higher incidence of insomnia symptoms (Daraj et al., 2023).

Research design and Methodology

This section explains the statistical techniques used for data analysis, covering both their application and the mathematical details.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

In this study Cross-Sectional study design was utilized and convenience sampling technique was used for data collection from 450 patients. For collection of primary data, Questionnaire method was used. The questionnaire consists of two portions; 1st part of questionnaire is asking questions from teenager and 2nd part of questionnaire is to ask questions from parents of those teenagers to check whether their excessive use of phone usage sets a norm that encourages similar behavior in their children.

Data Analysis Method

Reliability test of questionnaire was tested through Reliability Analysis.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) is used when the researcher has a specific theoretical model in mind based on prior research or theory and specifies which variables are expected to load on which factors. CFA is a multivariate technique used to test the hypothesis that a relationship between observed variables and their underlying latent constructs exists. In CFA it is observed that how many variations explained by the measured variables in a specific factor. CFA is used to confirm our theoretical model by determining whether these relationships are true.

Multinomial Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression is used when dependent variable is categorical. Multinomial logistic regression is a statistical method that helps analyze how various factors impact decisions or outcomes with three or more categories. Unlike binary regression, which is used for two outcomes, this method is specifically designed for scenarios where the dependent variable can take on multiple unordered categories.

It computes the probability of each category based on the values of the predictor variables. This technique identifies the most significant factors in predicting each outcome, demonstrating how changes in these factors affect the likelihood of each category. Overall, it provides a thorough understanding of the relationships between multiple predictors and a categorical outcome with more than two options. In this research Multinomial Logistic Regression is used with dependent variable having multiple categories i.e. Teenager mobile addiction time (a) Less than 2 hour (b) 3- 4hours (c) More than 5 hours.

Results Discussion and Conclusion

Firstly, the reliability of scale is measured. Then, the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is used after exploring these factors confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is used to confirm those factors. For checking the level that how much addiction of blue light teenagers have multinomial logistic regression is used.

Reliability Analysis

Reliability is tested by using Cronbach's Alpha which is found to be 0.798 which tells the internal consistency is on good level for dealing with complex constructs.

Exploratory Factor Analysis

The KMO test abbreviated from Kaiser Meyer Olkin and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity are used to check that data is enough for factor analysis. KMO value ranges from 0 to 1, and values near 1 show that data is good for factor analysis. KMO is found to be 0.804 shows in Table 3.1 which tells that sample size selected for research purpose is good enough for factor analysis. Bartlett's test determines if the Correlation Matrix is different from an identity matrix, which shows that the variables or questions in questionnaire are not correlated. A p-value of 0.000 (below 0.05) suggests that the correlations among the variables are strong enough for factor analysis. Bartlett's test significance is 0.00 tells that our all questions (variables) are suitable for factor analysis.

Table 1

KMO and Bartle test

KM	O and Bartle Test	
KMO Value		.804
Bartlett's Test Value	Approx. Chi-Square	3452.126
	Degree of freedom	120
	Significance	.000

Table 2

Total Communalities

	Total Communalities	
	Initial Communalities	Extraction Communalities
A1	1.000	.886
A2	1.000	.874
A3	1.000	.871
A4	1.000	.383
A5	1.000	.425
A6	1.000	.372
A7	1.000	.393
T1	1.000	.877
T2	1.000	.202
T3	1.000	.630
T4	1.000	.660
T5	1.000	.759
T6	1.000	.831
T7	1.000	.889
T8	1.000	.698
T9	1.000	.844

Table 2 shows the Communalities in a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) which shows how much of each variable's variation is explained by extracted factors. The table includes both the initial and extracted communalities for each variable. In initial communalities, each variable starts with a value of 1.000, which represents 100% contribution. This indicates that all variance is considered before any extraction occurs. In case of extracted communalities, it shows how much each variable contributes to the factor. Table shows that “A1” plays 88.6% role in making factor. In simple words, 88.6% of variation in factor is explained due to A1. similarly, “A2” has 87.4% role in making factor and so on.

Table 3

Total Variance Explained

	Initial eigenvalues			Extraction SS Loadings			Rotation SS Loadings		
	Over all	Num of Variance	Cumulative values	Over all	Num of Variance	Cumulative values	Over all	Num of Variance	Cumulative value
1	3.684	23.023	23.023	3.684	23.023	23.023	3.653	22.832	22.832
2	2.847	17.793	40.816	2.847	17.793	40.816	2.748	17.176	40.008
3	2.535	15.843	56.659	2.535	15.843	56.659	2.630	16.436	56.444
4	1.528	9.550	66.209	1.528	9.550	66.209	1.562	9.765	66.209
5	.941	5.879	72.088						

6	.877	5.482	77.569
7	.783	4.895	82.464
8	.737	4.607	87.072
9	.505	3.153	90.225
10	.398	2.485	92.710
11	.329	2.054	94.764
12	.210	1.312	96.075
13	.189	1.184	97.259
14	.163	1.020	98.280
15	.160	1.001	99.280
16	.115	.720	100.000

Table 3 shows the total variance explained it basically tells how much number of factors will be made in our factor analysis. And how variation our factors are explained. Firstly, by focusing on initial eigen value total column, number of components in which eigen values are greater than 1 this is actual number of factors. There are total 1st 4 components (rows) in which initial eigen value are greater than 1 so number of factors will be 4. Next, in rotated sum of square = 66.209 tells that overall, four factors explained 66.2% variation. 22.8% variation is explained from factor 1. whereas, 17.17% variation is explained from factor 2. while, 16.43% variation is explained from factor 3. At last, 9.76% variation is explained from factor 4. Rotated component matrix tells which variable will be go on which factor.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

CFA is used to test and confirm whether the data fits a hypothesized model. CFA validate the relationship between these factors that derive from EFA to ensure they are truly representation of our data.

Figure 1

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Fig 1 shows four factors which represents in oval shape, in box shape these are indicators, each indicator has an error term which is represented in circle shape. This diagram depicts a confirmatory factor analysis that outlines the connections between four latent variables (shown as ovals) and their related observed variables (shown as squares). The latent variable includes parent mobile addiction, parental addiction cause teenager cell addiction

teenager mobile addiction, and teenager social media addiction. These variables reflect the addiction of mobile. Each latent variable is connected to multiple observed variables (i.e. T1, T2, etc.) via arrows, which signify the extent to which each observed variable is affected by its corresponding latent variable. The numbers on these arrows, known as factor loadings, indicate the strength of the relationship between the latent and observed variables. Furthermore, each observed variable is associated with an error term (noted as e1, e2, etc.), which accounts for the variability in the observed variable that is not explained by the latent variable.

Table 4
Regression Weights (Initial /Default Model)

			Estimates	Standard Error	Critical Region.	significance
T7	<--	parentmobile_addiction	1.000			
T1	<--	parentmobile_addiction	.996	.029	34.85	***
T9	<--	parentmobile_addiction	.960	.032	29.83	***
T6	<--	parentmobile_addiction	.973	.031	30.92	***
T2	<--	parentmobile_addiction	.355	.052	6.789	***
T5	<--	ction_cause_teenager_cell_addiction	1.000			
T8	<--	ction_cause_teenager_cell_addiction	.912	.058	15.65	***
T4	<--	ction_cause_teenager_cell_addiction	.896	.060	14.95	***
T3	<--	ction_cause_teenager_cell_addiction	.920	.064	14.48	***
A1	<--	teenager_mobile_addiction	1.000			
A2	<--	teenager_mobile_addiction	.930	.034	27.10	***
A3	<--	teenager_mobile_addiction	.952	.036	26.71	***
A4	<--	teenager_socialmedia_addiction	1.000			
A5	<--	teenager_socialmedia_addiction	1.167	.307	3.803	***
A6	<--	teenager_socialmedia_addiction	1.100	.290	3.797	***
A7	<--	teenager_socialmedia_addiction	.802	.232	3.457	***

Table 4 illustrates the connections between latent variables and their observed counterparts. For parent mobile addiction, the observed variables T7, T1, T9, and T6 exhibit very strong correlations, with factor loadings nearing or reaching 1.000. These correlations are statistically significant, as shown by their high critical ratios (C.R.) and very low p-values (***). For example, T1 has a factor loading of 0.996, and small standard error (0.029), and a critical ratio of 34.851, indicating a solid relationship with parent mobile addiction. In contrast, T2 shows a considerably lower factor loading of 0.355, indicating a weaker connection with parent mobile addiction, although it remains statistically significant (C.R. = 6.789).

In the case of parental addiction cause teenager cell addiction, observed variables such as T5, T8, T4, and T3 also reveal strong associations. For instance, T8 has a factor loading of 0.912 and a critical ratio of 15.658, signifying a strong link with parental addiction cause teenager cell addiction. When examining teenager mobile addiction, the observed variables A1, A2, and A3 show high factor loadings, particularly A1, which shows a perfect factor loading of 1.000, indicating a strong and dependable relationship. Both A2 and A3 also present high loadings (0.930 and 0.952, respectively), accompanied by significant critical ratios, reflecting strong ties to teenager mobile addiction. Lastly, for teenager social media addiction, the observed variables A5, A6, and A7 demonstrate somewhat weaker, yet still significant, relationships. A5 has a factor loading of 1.167 with a critical ratio of 3.803, while A6 and A7 have factor loadings of 1.100 and 0.802, respectively. Although these values are lower than those of other variables in the model, they continue to be statistically significant. In conclusion, the model reveals strong connections between the variables. Here, Estimate = 0.996: The estimate of 0.996 tells the direction as well as strength of the relationship between Factor1 and (indicator) T1. Since, value of estimate is close to 1, it shows perfect positive association between T1 and Factor 1. Standard error = 0.029, Standard error of 0.029 is very low, shows that the estimate that we are doing are 0.996 highly precise. There is very little variation in this estimate, that makes us confident that 0.996 is an accurate image of the relationship between T1 and Factor 1.

Table 5*CMIN Significance*

Overall models	N PaR	CMIN	Degree Of Freedom	P value	CMIN/DF
Default/Initial model	54	130.163	98	.017	1.328
Maximized model	152	.000	0		
Null model	32	3506.317	120	.000	29.219

Table 5 shows the in-default model, CMIN (Chi-Square Value). The chi-square value for this model stands at 130.163, indicating the disparity between the predicted and actual covariance matrices. A smaller chi-square value indicates a more accurate model fit. The p-value obtained from the chi-square test is 0.017. For an ideal model fit, this value should be exceeded from 0.05, which tells that there is no significant difference between the model's predictions and the actual data. In this case, p-value is below 0.05, indicating that the model shows a good fit.

CMIN/DF (Relative Chi-Square): The Chi-Square by their degrees of freedom ratio stands at 1.328, a commonly referenced fit index. A value under 2.0 is seemed a good fit, indicating that the model aligns well with the data. In this case, the 1.328 value implies that the default model fits the data adequately.

Table 6*CFI Significance*

Overall model	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
Default/ Initial model	.963	.955	.991	.988	.991
Maximized model	1.000		1.000		1.000
Null model	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Table 7*RMSEA Significance*

Model	RMSEA	LO 90	HI 90	PCLOSE
Default/ Initial model	.029	.013	.041	.999
Null/ Independence model	.266	.258	.274	.000

Table 6 shows the CFI (Comparative Fit Index) and rho2 (ρ^2) are used to evaluate for which a model aligns with the data well, with ranges from 0 to 1, where 1 means a perfect fit of model. Here, the Default model shows a CFI of .991 and a rho2 of .991, both indicating a great fit to the data.

Table 7 shows The Root Mean Square Error of Approximation also named as RMSEA shows how well a model matches the data. For the Initial model also named as Default model, RMSEA is 0.029, indicating a very good fit since values under 0.05 are usually seen as excellent. The LO 90 and HI 90 values (0.013 and 0.041) provide the 90% confidence interval for the RMSEA, suggesting that we are 90% confident that actual RMSEA value will be fall within this range.

Multinomial Logistic Regression

Table 8*Overall Model Fitness*

All Model	Model Fitness Checking			LRT		
	AIC	BIC	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	DF	P value
Intercept Only	736.013	743.991	732.013			
Final	733.998	765.910	717.998	14.015	6	.029

Table 9*Chi square and significance*

	Chi Square	DF	Significance.
Pearson-value	616.605	612	.440
Deviance-value	644.275	612	.177

Table 10

Square's

Pseudo R Sqr	
Cox & Snell	.035
Nagel kerke	.040
Mc Fadden	.017

Table 11

All Variable Significances

	AIC	BIC	-2 Log Likelihood of Reduced Model	Chi Square	DF	P value
Alpha Value	733.537	757.471	721.537	3.539	2	.170
age_teenager	731.753	755.687	719.753	1.755	2	.416
teenager_mobile_addiction_TMA	736.869	760.803	724.869	6.871	2	.032
teenager_socialmedia_	735.220	759.154	723.220	5.221	2	.073

Table 12

Odd Ratios

cellusetime_teenager^a		Beta	SE	Wald CI	Df	Significance	Exp(B)	95% Confidence Interval for Exp(B)	
								Lower value	Upper value
less than 2 hour	Alpha Value	-1.500	.806	3.464	1	.063			
	age_teenager	.017	.037	.217	1	.641	1.017	.946	1.094
	teenager_mobile_addiction_TMA	.013	.040	.104	1	.747	1.013	.937	1.095
	teenager_socialmedia_usage_TSU	.015	.040	.138	1	.711	1.015	.938	1.098
	Intercept	-.486	.708	.472	1	.492			
3 to 4 hour	age_teenager	-.032	.032	1.045	1	.307	.968	.910	1.030
	teenager_mobile_addiction_TMA	-.083	.035	5.500	1	.019	.921	.859	.987
	teenager_socialmedia_usage_TSU	.080	.036	5.006	1	.025	1.084	1.010	1.163

Table 8 shows that p value = 0.029 which is less than 0.05 (threshold) means that adding all predictor variables in final model shows a significantly difference compared to alpha based model also named as intercept model. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) value in table 3.11 is used to compare the model fitness between multiple models. The lower value of AIC shows the best fit of the data. In our case, AIC =733 tells that model is best fit. It balances model complexity and fit by penalizing over other complex models. Only value of AIC of single model doesn't say that whether a model is "good" or "bad" but it can be says good or bad when we are comparing multiple models. Here, AIC of final model is less then as compared to default model so we can say that final model has a good fit. Table 9 shows the P value is 0.440, which is much higher than the standard threshold of 0.05. This suggests that there is no significant differ between model's predictions and the actual observations. Thus, model fits the data well. The Deviance statistic shows how well model performs as compared to saturated model. Here, the p-value is 0.177, which is greater than 0.05. This means the difference between model and the saturated model is not statistically significant. Therefore, model is seemed to fit the data well based on the Deviance test.

Table 10 shows Pseudo R-Square which tells how well our predictors can be explained by the outcome (Dependent Variable). Value of Cox and Snell is 0.035 which tells that 3.5% of the deviation in the dependent variable is due to these independent variables. Nagel kerke (0.040): This value shows that 4% of the variation in

the dependent variable are explained by these independent variables. McFadden (0.017) which tells 1.7% of the variation is explained by dependent variable occur due to these independent variables. These low values shows that the independent variables that were added in the model only tells a small part of the variation in dependent variable. Which means other unconsidered factors which were not add in model likely play a bigger role. In Table 12 tells that which variable has significant effect on model hypothesis. This means that removing the intercept does not significantly impact the model fit. This means that removing the variable TMA significantly impact the model fit.

Conclusion

This study examined how blue light becomes a reason for teenagers to addict their mobile phone. Moreover, how parental excessive usage of mobile phone also becomes a reason for teenager to use mobile phone excessively. In this study, teenager mobile addiction is dependent variable and blue light exposure and parental excessive usage are independent variables. Reliability Analysis, Exploratory Factor Analysis, Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Multinomial Logistic Regression are utilized for analysis of data.

The research finds that teenage mobile addiction is influenced by parents and the harmful effects of blue light. More-ever, study revealed that both of these independent variables have significant impact on teenagers' mobile addiction. When parents are often on their phones, they set an example that their children tend to follow. This behavior normalizes excessive phone use, leading to addictive habits in teens. Teenagers who use mobile phone 5 or more than 5 hours are being addicted to their mobile phone and most of them are addicted by seeing their parents too much mobile usage. Additionally, the study points out that blue light from screens worsens the problem.

Recommendation & Suggestion

In this study, non-probability sampling techniques is used for data collection due to shortage of time and resources. It is suggested that probability sampling techniques should be used for data collection which can control biasness and obtain valid results. Due to limitation of use, we use cross sectional design. It is suggested to use longitudinal design and see in how much time blue light effects on teenager mental health. It is also suggested that parent's excessive usage has a significant impact on teenager to become mobile addiction. While it is suggested to give a new dimension of study that how to control these negative impacts. The study recommends that changing parental phone habits and limiting blue light exposure could help reduce mobile addiction in teenagers, benefiting their mental health and well-being and develop guidelines for blue light use.

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